

The COVID-19 vaccine is available for many children under age 17. However, most child vaccination requires parental/guardian consent. Therefore, researchers at the University of Arkansas for Medical Sciences studied whether parents planned to vaccinate their children and what factors may affect that decision.

WHERE:

Across the United States

WHEN?

September 7 to October 3, 2021

WHO?

2,022 US Parents/Guardians (age ≥ 18 years) with a child age ≤ 17 years

THE POPULATION (descriptive about Who):

The survey participants were mostly from minority populations (average):

- 28% Hispanic/Latino
- 22% Black
- 9% Asian American
- 7% Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander
- 7% Native American or Alaska Native

The study purposely did not combine Asian American with Native Hawaiian / Pacific Islander as many other studies do.

WHAT HAPPENED:

The study team recruited survey participants from an opt-in panel of research volunteers.

Participants completed a 10-minute online survey which asked about:

- Plan to vaccinate child(ren)
- Demographics
- Health coverage status
- Personal vaccination status
- Political affiliation
- History of COVID-19 infection
- Exposure to COVID-19 death
- Social norms
- COVID-19 vaccine concern

The study team split the survey answers into two groups based on the age of the participants' oldest child:

- Oldest child aged 12-17 and eligible for vaccination
- Oldest child aged 11 or younger and not yet eligible for vaccination

This summary was performed in December 2022. This summary includes only the results of a single study. Other studies may find different results. The study was supported by the NIH RADx[®] Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) initiative.

Citation: Willis DE, Schootman M, Shah SK, Reece S, Selig JP, Andersen JA, McElfish PA. Parent/guardian intentions to vaccinate children against COVID-19 in the United States. *Human Vaccines & Immunotherapeutics*. 2022; 18(5):e2071078. Doi: 10.1080/21645515.2022.2071078

To read the published research article, visit radx-up.org.

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KEY FINDINGS

Oldest child ≤ 11

Oldest child 12–17

Already vaccinated	-----	31%
Plan to vaccinate right away	36%	31%
Wait and See	36%	17%
Only if required	10%	10%
Definitely Not	17%	11%

Highest Prevalence of Factors for Child Vaccination

Parent/Guardian's Intent to Vaccinate Child, Oldest child ≤ 11

Parent/Guardian Already Vaccinated Child, Oldest child 12-17

No Hesitancy	66%	45%
Nearly all people close to them vaccinated	68%	39%
Parents/Guardians had at least one vaccine dose	53%	40%
Some College, but No Degree	-----	39%
Democrat	50%	39%
Asian American	68%	55%

Highest Prevalence of Parent / Guardian's Intent Not to Vaccinate

Oldest child ≤ 11

Oldest child 12–17

Parent/Guardian Not Vaccinated	40%	33%
Very Few People Close to Them Vaccinated	35%	40%
Republican	27%	24%
Native American or Alaska Native	27%	23%
Uninsured	-----	26%

CONCLUSIONS/RECOMMENDATIONS:

Intention to vaccinate children was significantly associated with age, education, political affiliation, social norms, COVID-19 vaccination status and COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy for parents/guardians of children in both age groups. Most parents with a child eligible for vaccination had either already vaccinated their child or planned to right away. Most parents with a child not yet eligible for vaccination either planned to vaccinate right away or wait and see. Findings suggest that barriers other than intent may hinder parents'/guardians' who indicated they would vaccinate their child(ren) right away but had not yet done so. Additionally, teasing apart racial/ethnic groups may reveal previously unknown gaps. For example, acknowledging the diverse attitudes and experiences of Asian Americans and Native Hawaiians / Pacific Islanders in this study revealed a wide gap in intention to vaccinate children. Finally, the results of this study may be useful when identifying groups and areas to target for vaccine campaigns. Public health officials should consider political party affiliation when developing messaging since it has become a source of identity for many people.

LIMITATIONS:

This study relied on cross-sectional data and does not make any causal claims.

This study relied on reports from parents/guardians; however, future research should include youth and parent-child dyads to assess differences in parent-child feelings about vaccination, especially in states where parental consent is not required for all minors.

